

Narrow and Broadband Low-noise Amplifiers at Higher Frequency using FDSOI CMOS Technology

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Abstract — This work demonstrates the successful implementation of two single-stage low-noise amplifiers (LNAs) using 0.18 μm fully depleted silicon on insulator (FDSOI) CMOS technology. These two amplifiers utilize a metal T-gate n-MOSFET device for improved RF performance. The narrowband LNA has a measured gain of 8.2 dB, a noise figure (NF) of 1.5 dB and input referred third order intercept point (IIP3) value of 12.8 dBm at 3.2 GHz. The broadband LNA has yielded a gain of 7.6 - 4.5 dB and a NF of 2.8 – 3.0 dB across 5 - 10 GHz. The measured IIP3 is 15.4 dBm at 8 GHz. The narrowband amplifier consumes 28.5 mW and the broadband amplifier consumes 54.5 mW of power, both at $V_{gs} = 0.75$ V and $V_{ds} = 1.0$ V. These two amplifiers have demonstrated the feasibility of FDSOI CMOS technology for phased array applications.

Index Terms — CMOS, FDSOI, LNA, IIP3, Broadband, Noise figure, Narrowband.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE monolithic integration of a large number of complex functions on a chip has been rising steadily at a very fast pace. The rapidly growing needs for wireless communications applications and high performance RF components for military sensors and telecommunications has increased the demands of RFIC designs. The purpose of these circuit designs is to explore the feasibility of the FDSOI CMOS technology for receiver-on-a-chip applications, where cost, weight, and power reduction are important metrics. The LNA is the most critical component in a receiver chain because it sets the noise performance of the system. The transistor used in these designs is a CMOS device with T-gate metal enhancement. The metal T-gate enhances the transistor performance by reducing the gate resistance and increasing the cutoff frequency (f_c). The FDSOI CMOS process is improved over the bulk CMOS process in terms of device isolation, high-Q inductor components, and RF/digital integration. With its simple process, suppressed short channel effect, reduced parasitic capacitance, and high packing density, the high speed low power FDSOI technology is suitable for full CMOS

system-on-a-chip integration [1]. The RF performance of these two amplifiers - gain, noise and linearity - demonstrate the suitability of the RF enhanced FDSOI CMOS technology in high frequency RF applications.

II. TECHNOLOGY DESCRIPTION

The SOI technology features a thick buried oxide, separating the handle wafer from the thin layer of silicon, used to create devices and there by isolating the devices from the substrate. The FDSOI CMOS process features single level poly and two interconnect metal layers and is improved for RF operations by utilizing a 2.1 μm thick top-level RF metal layer. The RF metal thickness was chosen to improve the line loss without sacrificing the digital circuit density and design cost. The substrate (i.e. handle wafer) in this case has a high resistivity (>3000 ohm-cm), and in conjunction with the buried oxide reduces the junction capacitance and the loss of passive components, such as inductors and transmission line, through substrate coupling [1]. Transistors are further isolated by a mesa etch applied to the thin silicon layer which etches away all non-active silicon at the top of the buried oxide. An additional process option allows the formation of the T-gate CMOS devices which feature a metal shunt on top of the polysilicon gate. The low gate resistance of the T-gate CMOS device significantly improves the frequency response resulting in performance enhancements for the f_c , the maximum frequency of oscillation (f_{max}), and the minimum noise figure (F_{min}) [1,2,3]. The FDSOI CMOS technology has a peak f_c of 67 GHz and f_{max} of 76 GHz for an n-MOSFET with metal-strapped T-gate [1]. Transmission lines as well as inductors are placed on the RF metal to minimize the resistive loss. The technology offers p-poly resistor with a sheet resistance of 20 Ohms/square, n-poly resistor of sheet resistance 20-27 Ohms/square, and metal-insulator-metal (MIM) capacitors. The capacitance per unit area of a single layer dielectric capacitor is 38 pF / mm^2 and the multi-layer dielectric capacitor is 60 pF / mm^2 .

III. CIRCUIT DESIGN

For technology demonstration, a narrowband LNA and a broadband LNA are designed to investigate the feasibility of FDSOI technology for X-Band phased array applications. Both circuits are single stage, single-ended amplifiers with input and output matched to 50 Ohm. All matching networks are implemented on-chip. A coplanar waveguide (CPW) topology is employed in the design of both amplifiers. Source inductive degeneration and output shunt resistors are incorporated to achieve stability of these two amplifiers [4]. The input network is matched to yield optimum noise performance while meeting the return loss specification and the output network is designed to yield maximum gain. A small series source inductance increases the input resistance, and it connects the source to ground to bring the optimum reflection coefficient closer to S_{11}^* [5]. Inductive degeneration is used to achieve simultaneous input impedance match and optimum noise match without any adverse impact on the device noise performance while trading off the amplifier gain degradation and linearity of the amplifier. Even though the FDSOI technology has a reduced insertion loss, due to high resistivity substrate, a CPW design is employed because this technology lacks a good backside ground which would be needed for a microstrip mode design. In order to suppress the undesired CPW mode of propagation, underpasses were used at all CPW transmission line discontinuities. To increase the self-resonance frequency of the inductor and to reduce the coupling, the ground plane has been removed from the surrounding area of the inductor [6]. Electromagnetic simulations (EM) were performed on all interconnects and inductors to ensure design accuracy.

A. Narrowband Amplifier Design

The narrowband LNA centered at 3.2 GHz is a single stage common source amplifier optimized for low noise and high linearity performance. The active device is a 10-finger n-MOSFET with a 20 μm unit gate width totaling 200 μm of gate periphery. Minimum noise figure and the associated gain of the 10x20 μm device is nominally 0.5 dB and 17 dB at 3.2GHz with $V_{ds}=1.0$ V and $V_{gs}=0.75$ V. The input impedance of a MOSFET is capacitive, so it is difficult to provide a good 50 Ohm match without degrading the noise performance. By implementing a 0.8 nH source inductive degeneration, this LNA achieved optimum noise and a high linearity matching condition across 2.7-3.7 GHz. The schematic of the S-band LNA is shown in Fig. 1. The input matching network is achieved by a 2nd order LC network. There is no additional output matching network other than a shunt resistor, for amplifier

stability. The size of the narrowband LNA is 2.5 mm x 2.0 mm. Fig. 2 shows the micrograph of the narrowband LNA.

Fig. 1. Schematic of narrowband LNA.

Fig. 2. Micrograph of narrowband LNA.

B. Broadband Amplifier Design

The broadband amplifier is designed to trade-off gain, noise figure, and linearity for wide bandwidth operation. The active device for this amplifier is a 20-finger n-MOSFET with a 20 μm unit gate width (20x20 μm of gate periphery). Minimum noise figure, associated gain, and output referred third order intercept point of a 20x20 μm device at 10 GHz is 1.3 dB, 11 dB, and 23 dBm, respectively, biased at 1.0 V drain voltage and 0.75 V gate voltage. Similarly to the narrow band amplifier, the broadband amplifier utilizes a single stage common source amplifier topology with source inductive degeneration to enable simultaneous 50 Ohm input matching, optimum noise matching and high linearity across the design frequency of 5-10 GHz. The schematic of the broadband amplifier is shown in Fig. 3. The input matching network

is achieved by a bandpass filter and the output matching is achieved by a 2nd order lowpass network. The chip dimensions of the amplifier are 1.91 mm x 1.7 mm. Fig. 4 shows the micrograph of the broadband LNA.

Fig. 3. Schematic of broadband LNA.

Fig. 4. Micrograph of broadband LNA.

IV. MEASURED RESULTS

To evaluate the small signal performance of the amplifiers, on-wafer testing was performed through the RF probe pads using Agilent's 8510B network analyzer in a 50 Ohm environment. The transistor is biased through the RF pads at $V_{ds} = 1.0$ V and $V_{gs} = 0.75$ V to set the drain current of the RF transistor. Noise parameters of the LNAs were measured using Agilent's N8970B noise figure meter. The third-order intercept point of the amplifiers was characterized using a Maury Microwave load pull system with the input/output tuners set to 50 Ohm with a tone spacing of 1MHz.

A. Narrowband Amplifier Characterization

Fig. 5 displays measured s-parameters of the amplifier from 2.5-4 GHz. Measured results show a 3 dB frequency bandwidth from 2.7 GHz to 3.7 GHz. The LNA yielded

Fig. 5. Measured s-parameters of the narrowband LNA.

small signal gain ranging from 9.5-6.5 dB across 2.7-3.7 GHz. The measured input return loss ($|S_{11}|$) and output return loss ($|S_{22}|$) remained below 10 dB across the frequency band of interest. The LNA has a measured noise figure of 1.3 – 1.7 dB across the frequency band. Fig. 6 shows NF and IIP3 with respect to frequency. As shown in the plot, measurements yielded an IIP3 of 12.8 dBm at 3.2 GHz. This LNA consumes 28.5 mW of power at $V_{gs} = 0.75$ V and $V_{ds} = 1$ V. The S-band LNA centered at 3.2 GHz has 31% bandwidth.

Fig. 6. Frequency vs. NF & IIP3 within the frequency band (2.7-3.7 GHz).

B. Broadband Amplifier Characterization

Measured S-parameters are displayed in Fig. 7. The broadband LNA has yielded a gain of 7.6-4.5 dB across 5-10 GHz. The measured input return loss ($|S_{11}|$) remained below 10 dB across the frequency band of operation, and the output return loss ($|S_{22}|$) is below 10 dB at the center and degrades at the lower frequency band of operation. Fig. 8 shows the two-tone measurement and NF with respect to frequency, which yielded an IIP3 of 15.4 dBm at 8 GHz. Measured noise figure is 2.8 - 3.0 dB across the design frequency. This broadband LNA consumes 54.5 mW of power at $V_{gs} = 0.75$ V and $V_{ds} = 1$ V. The broadband amplifier centered at 7.5 GHz has 67 % bandwidth.

Fig. 7. Measured s-parameters of the broadband LNA.

Fig. 8. Frequency vs. NF & IIP3 within the frequency band (5 - 10 GHz).

V. CONCLUSION

This work advances the state-of-the-art for LNA design by demonstrating the feasibility of CMOS FDSOI technology for microwave applications extending to X-Band. Both narrowband and broadband amplifiers are designed to illustrate the trade-off between noise figure, gain and bandwidth. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the S-band amplifier yielded the lowest noise figure reported at 1.5 dB. The broadband amplifier achieved the lowest reported noise figure for a broadband MMIC in CMOS technology. Finally, both amplifiers exhibited excellent IIP3 across S-X band operation.

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